

1 **A hematopoietic phenotype in humans with Crohn's Disease.**

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The phenotype was heterogenous and included dysregulation of cellularity in erythroid (anemia), lymphoid and myeloid (neutropenia) compartments. Hematopoietic defects observed in patients with IBD included bone marrow failure phenotypes that possessed a stress component likely related to a DNA repair defect and complicated at times by cellular stress resulting from extended nutritional deficiencies.

9 Citations

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